

The Soil Re-Union Science for Healthy Soils

4th International and
16th National Congress
of the Serbian Society
of Soil Science

Serbian
Society of
Soil Science

THE BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Vrdnik, Fruške Terme, Serbia,
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Soil ReUnion: Science speaks – a call to united action

Humanity faces a triple crisis: climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution. The international community is working intensively to address these challenges, and science confirms that the *wise use of soil* remains one of the most effective levers for protecting ecosystems and advancing climate action. Soil is, more than ever, at the center of global attention, both a joy and a responsibility for all of us who care for it.

The Soil ReUnion Congress, though not a massive world assembly, carries big ideas. Its ambition, as an initial spark, is to contribute to the global effort of responding to the triple crisis, through a triple unification, bringing together: sectors, regions, and disciplines around soil.

Agriculture, in particular, is increasingly recognized as a field that can both mitigate and adapt to climate change through regenerative practices - creating an entire *generation of regeneration*. This transition requires practical knowledge, faster research, and innovative approaches such as Living Labs, since we no longer have time for a “trial and error” approach. And let us not forget: 95% of the world’s food comes from soil, and despite technological advancements, there is no energy sustainable alternative that could ever fully replace agricultural land.

Our congress brings together scientists, decision-makers, business representatives, and global initiatives to contribute voices, ideas, and perspectives that can enrich the broader movement for soil protection. Its impact is designed to extend beyond the event itself - creating a unique community of like-minded professionals through a vibrant social program, project presentations, and our innovative π to π format: project-to-project speed blind dates.

The congress goals provide a clear framework - and we warmly invite you to find your place within it, connect with others, and make the most of every opportunity it offers, including:

- transferring scientific knowledge to bridge science, industry, and policy;
- creating a platform for dialogue to enable cooperation and co-creation of future strategies; and
- establishing thematic networks to ensure ongoing knowledge exchange and advance soil protection beyond the event.

Welcome - and thank you for being part of this shared contribution!

Dr Jordana Ninkov, president of Organization committee

Dr Snežana Jakšić, president of Program committee

Dr Jovica Vasin, president of Scientific committee and president of Serbian Society of Soil Science

EXCERPT FROM THE CONGRESS PROGRAMME

This extract from the official Congress Programme captures the spirit and concept of the Congress. The complete and detailed programme has been published separately.

Duration: 20–23 October 2025

Venue: Fruške Terme Hotel, Vrdnik, Serbia

Congress Centre: IV Floor, Wing B

Monday, 20 October 2025

Late afternoon

Registration

Fireside chat and interactive discussion

Dinner

Welcome party

Tuesday, 21 October 2025

Morning session

Registration

Official ceremonial opening of the Congress

Pause, Project exhibitions tour

Pause, Poster viewing session

Plenary lectures – Keynote speakers

Parallel oral presentations

Lunch

Pause for forest walk or relaxation

Afternoon session

Interactive workshop on innovative techniques in soil analysis and nutrient management (Sponsors' exhibition)

π to π (Project-to-Project) speed blind date

Dinner

Social gathering

Wednesday, 22 October 2025

Registration

Parallel oral presentations

Pause, Poster viewing session

Poster section with three-minute talks

Lunch

Assembly of the Serbian Society of Soil Science

Pause for forest walk or relaxation

Gala dinner

Thursday, 23 October 2025

Expert and tourist excursion – one-day

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(in alphabetical order)

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INFLUENCE OF SELECTED ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS ON THE SORPTION OF 2,4-DB

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ABSTRACT

2,4-DB (4-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)butanoic acid) belongs to the group of herbicides from the phenoxy acid class, with soil processes such as sorption, degradation, and mobility determining its impact on the environment. The mobility of 2,4-DB is largely determined by its physico-chemical properties and the characteristics of the soil, with sorption playing a crucial role in controlling its fate. Various types of organic soil amendments (OSA), such as biochar and sewage sludge, are commonly applied for soil remediation. The objective of this study was to investigate sorption of 2,4-DB to Bayreuth soil and to assess the influence of OSA on its retention.

Column experiments using HPLC were performed under varying pH and ionic strength of the fresh water solution dissolving calcium chloride (CaCl₂) and magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) in Milli-Q water. The concentrations of 2,4-DB spiked to the columns were 10, 50, and 100 mg/L.

With the addition of biochar and sewage sludge to the soil column, the distribution coefficient (K_d) of 2,4-DB generally increased. This effect can be attributed to the presence of functional groups, such as phenolic, carbonyl, and hydroxyl groups, in biochar and sludge, which, as organic soil amendments, enable their interaction with 2,4-DB through hydrogen bonding, dipole–dipole interactions, and electrostatic forces, thereby contributing to its retention in the soil.

HPLC column experiments indicate that organic soil amendments enhance 2,4-DB retention, thereby reducing its mobility and concentration.

Key words: soil, organic soil amendments, 4-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)butanoic acid, sorption

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